

Social Insecurity and the Development of Tourism in Nigeria: the Niger Delta Experience, 2004 –2009

Blessing Okwuchi Nwagba, PhD¹; CHUKWU, Christian Chima, PhD² & Grace A.T
Scent, PhD³

¹Executive Director, Fulfillment International Schools, Aba, Abia State, Nigeria. ORCID: 0000-0002-8261-3534.

²Department of Sociology, Novena University, Ogume, Delta State, Nigeria. ORCID: 0000-0002-4290-234X.

³Department of Sociology and Anthropology, Niger Delta University, Wilberforce Island, Nigeria. ORCID: 0000-0001-8846-6881.

ABSTRACT:

Social insecurity is increasingly becoming a permanent feature of the Nigerian social formation. The Niger Delta region of South-south Nigeria has had more than a fair share of social insecurity which is believed to have adversely affected industries and tourism industry in particular. It is on this premise that this study sets out to investigate the impact of social insecurity on development of tourism and hospitality industry in Niger-Delta region of Nigeria between 2004 and 2009. Three hypotheses were formulated and tested using test inferential statistics at 95% level of significance. The study adopted a survey research designs and three hundred and forty-five (345) respondents were purposively selected from the sampled states. A structured questionnaire tagged: Social insecurity and tourism development questionnaire was used to gather data. This instrument had a reliability co-efficient (SITNDQ) of $r=0.8$ and it was the main instrument used for data collection. The data collected were analyzed using percentage, mean and standard deviation scores, while the Z-test statistics was employed to test the hypotheses. The results obtained showed among others, that social insecurity negatively impacted on tourism development in the Niger Delta region within the period of study. Secondly, there was also a very strong association between the level of social insecurity and downward trends in all the measured variables: growth in tourism, foreign direct investment, and employment generation within the period of study. Based on these findings the study concluded that issues concerning poverty, unequal access to resources, and large youth populations with limited access to education or jobs, and other socio-political factors which contributed to the prevalence of social insecurity in the region should be addressed. Sequel to this, the study recommended that the government should critically address the welfare and developmental needs of the people of the Niger Delta region as a proper articulation of policies to address these issues will ward-off social insecurity and restore social order. Again, as a socio-economic activity that has the potential of raising the standards of living of the people, government should create awareness that tourism development is a sure way to eradicate abject poverty among rural communities in the region. Finally, since investors in the tourism industry are concerned about the security of their investments, and as well as their personal safety of tourists, government should direct effort towards modernizing the security agencies and institutions, and also seek assistance from developed countries to enhance the operational capabilities of the country's security agencies.

KEYWORDS: *Employment generation; Foreign direct investment; Niger Delta region; Social insecurity; Tourism and Hospitality Industry;*

I. INTRODUCTION

There is no doubt that social insecurity has increasingly become a permanent feature of the Nigerian social formation. The raison d'être for this faulty foundation, according to scholars, is that Nigeria, an erstwhile British colony, boycotted the due process of legitimization at creation. In other words, from inception till date, the notion of Nigeria is still being seen as a mere geographic expression because its configuration comprises of the

forceful packaging of unwilling communities of diverse origin and culture under the same polity through colonial authoritarian fiat [8]. From the onset, it was glaring that the British knew what they wanted from coercing all these unenthusiastic communities into a Nation-State via amalgamation. Despite being aware that it contradicted the freedom of association enshrined in the UN charter, Lord Lugard went ahead with the amalgamation. Writing on this defect, Shively [32] said Nigeria like most British colonies was not constructed for internal coherence, but rather for British administrative convenience. Since then, relations and political behaviour of the peoples have been characterized by mutual suspicion and invidious hatred as nothing seems to bind them. This fragile oneness seems to explain why the notorious group, Boko Haram, an originally unorganized group, according to Nwagba [23], has metamorphosed into a fearful terrorist group, and has been terrorizing the political landscape of the country for the past fifteen years now. Its terrorist posture against the Nigerian state has been hinged on the instrumentality of religion, and the use of instruments of violence to continue to usher in mass destruction, social and political turmoil in the country, particularly in the northern part. Unfortunately, the cycle of violence unleashed on Nigerians, according to Adagba, Ugwu & Eme[1] by the fundamentalist group, Boko Haram has heightened fears among the populace because the resentment has gone beyond religion or political colouration.

In agreement with the flawed foundation of the country, the Niger Delta region of Southern Nigeria has had more than a fair share of political and social instability. However, while the social instability in the Niger Delta could be associated with the non-use of the vast revenue accruing from the resources therein for the development of the region, the Boko Haram brouhaha remains unjustifiable. The Niger Delta region is home to Nigeria's crude oil and gas reserves. In other words, the area provides oil wealth for the bulk of Nigeria's foreign earnings, and also houses a vast and extensive oil and gas infrastructure. This rich endowment accounts for over 80% of Nigeria's revenue, foreign earnings, and exports. Ironically, the vast revenue from the resources has hardly been for the development of the region. There is nothing to show for years of degradation and pollution except poverty, loss of aquatic life and poor standard of living from the exploration and exploitation of oil for decades. According to Ifeanacho[16], this has caused a lot of conflict as youths have risen up to protest against this age long deprivation. Writing earlier, Lawan[20] contend that the region grapples with the shackles of poverty, illiteracy, diseases, among others. The Niger Delta region is home to Nigeria's crude oil and gas reserves. It also houses a vast and extensive oil and gas infrastructure. This rich endowment accounts for 85% of Nigeria's revenue, foreign earnings, and exports. Regrettably, the region where this wealth is being generated from has suffered marginalization, poor governance, underdevelopment, unequal distribution of wealth, and exemption from the oil economy of the country.

Despite the Amnesty programme granted the agitators, the region still grapple with the shackles of poverty, illiteracy, diseases, among others. A report by the United Nations Development Programme, (UNDP) in [36] titled "Niger Delta Human Report," cited in Ugwulebo [38] shows that the region recorded over 6,800 oil spills between 1976 and 2001, with a loss of approximately 3 million barrels of oil. A report by Amnesty International titled "Nigeria: Petroleum, Pollution and Poverty in the Niger Delta" says that for the past 50 years the region has experienced "oil spills" at par with the Exxon Valdez every year. The report states that between 9 million and 13 million barrels had leaked in the five decades of oil operations. To this, Onu [27], Osuigwe [29] and many other scholars are in agreement that the Delta region is a place of frustrated mistrust. Unprecedented restiveness, at times, erupts into violence. Long years of neglect and conflict have fostered a siege mentality especially among youths. They feel they are condemned to a future without hope and have resorted to conflict as a strategy to escape deprivation. Evidently, the social insecurity developed in the system had obvious impact on the industrial development of the Niger Delta region. The United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Niger Delta Human Development Report issued in [36] portrays the often cited contradiction of huge oil wealth derivable from the region and the state of development thus:

Its rich endowments of oil and gas resources feed methodically into the international economic system, in exchange for massive revenues that carry the promise of rapid socio-economic transformation within the delta itself. In reality, the Niger Delta is a region suffering from administrative neglect, crumbling social infrastructure and

services, high unemployment, social deprivation, abject poverty, filth and squalor, and endemic conflict (1) [36].

Consequent upon these identified several grievances including the poor state of development; abject poverty in the midst of plenty; absence of basic social amenities; corporate irresponsibility associated with oil companies operations; a regional agitation for development was ushered in. Put simply, the lack of cooperate responsibilities from the activities of oil companies, such as environmental pollution and degradation, the deep declines in derivation based oil revenues as well as the existence of a highly centralize federal structure that left states in the Niger Delta region at a disadvantage generated agitations[10]. Confirming this ugly trend, Onu [27] Osuigwe [29] and many other scholars upheld that the Delta region is a place of frustrated mistrust. Unprecedented restiveness, at times, erupts into violence. Long years of neglect and conflict have fostered a siege mentality especially among youths. They feel they are condemned to a future without hope and have resorted to conflict as a strategy to escape deprivation.

Basically, these agitations rested on popular and civil group mobilization which began first at individual community level and later cumulated into a region wide militia protest for resource control, revenue allocation, development and inclusion in the oil economy [10]. From this discourse, it is obvious to comprehend how social insecurity developed and impacted negatively on the industrial development of the Niger Delta region, particularly on tourism and hospitality industry. As stated earlier, the restiveness and the struggle for fair distribution of what is obtained in their land assumed dangerous integers and snowballed into kidnapping and other social vices. According to Ugwulebo [38] companies were fast leaving restive and kidnap – prone areas. Many expatriate staffs of companies were kidnapped thereby forcing others to flee. Regrettably, when kidnapping was extended to local staff and entrepreneurs, many business operations were either closed down or out-rightly liquidated in the Niger Delta area. Substantiating, Ugwulebo [38] argues that since the indigenous entrepreneurs started being hunted by kidnapers, the story has never been the same. Most businesses were closed down because some of those kidnapped and who later regained their freedom, used their working capital and even borrowed more money running into millions of naira to secure their freedom. Having been weakened by the magnitude of ransom paid, abandoning the region was an option which could not be faulted. What is even more, no entrepreneur is willing to site his business in a restive and conflict-ridden area. Restiveness and the insurgency in the region impacted negatively on industrial development, tourism and hospitality industries in particular. Conclusively, Onu [27] and Osuigwe [29] aver that the events that culminated into the state of social insecurity were age long, but little by little, it began from the demonstration for control of oil resources, particularly crude oil by the indigenous people of the Niger Delta region and eventually snowballed to become a hotbed for violent conflicts and insurgency. In all these, socio-economic development, foreign investment and employment opportunities declined significantly owing to social insecurity as prospective investors became unenthusiastic about investing in the region.

Despite these, it is important to acknowledge that the Niger Delta region has numerous tourism attraction sites which social insecurity has negatively impacted upon. These included Oloibiri oil museum, State transit hall and Ogidi shrine in Bayelsa State. In Rivers State, there are the Isaac Boro Park, King Jaja of Opobo Monument, Port-Harcourt Tourist beach, Port Harcourt zoo and Okirika Aquatic stadium, Abraka River Resort, Obudu Cattle Ranch, the Kwa falls and Tinapa[21]. The National War museum and monument, The Azumini Blue River, the museum of colonial history and the Arochukwu caves, Benin Bronze, Museums, Art Galleries, Historic sites, Parks, among others. Since the Nigerian Tourism Development Corporation Act provided a legal framework for tourism development in the country, some of the enormous human and material resources developed into festivals are Calabar Christmas Carnival, Rivers State Festival of Arts and Culture (Rivfest Carnival currently known as carnival) among others [14]. Undeniably, tourism has over the years distinguished itself as one of the major tools for income generation and poverty alleviation in a developing country like Nigeria. However, with the poor state of social instability and insecurity of all sorts, socio-economic development, foreign direct investment, and employment generation suffered greatly.

In view of the foregoing, this present study placed its searchlight on the impact of social insecurity on tourism and hospitality industries with a view to understanding how the state of tourism and the hospitality industry can be improved upon in the Niger Delta region.

1.2 Statement of the problem

From the foregoing analysis, the vast tourism potentials in the Niger Delta provide windows of opportunities for socio-economic development, foreign direct investment, and employment generation. These potentials, according to Larry [21] cited in Eja, Ukwayi and Ojong[13], range from natural to man-made such as the table mountain, colourful folks, beautiful landscape, overwhelming serenity and agreeable climate welcoming fun seekers to the highlands of Niger Delta. However, these potentials alone are not sufficient to attract tourists because these destinations are less appealing to tourists if they are insecure or likely to experience serious conflict [5]. Security and stable polity provide the *sine qua non* for tourism development. Not only is tourism vulnerable to social insecurity it is diametrically opposed to insecurity. In spite of the enormous tourism potentials in the region, the region is yet to translate into a tourist destination as a result of inherent social insecurity. However, none of the many scholarly researches, to the best of our knowledge, have delved into the menace of social insecurity on tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta Region. The effects of social insecurity provoked by youth restiveness on the socio-economic development, foreign investment, and generation of employment opportunities in the tourism sector were ignored.

Based on the foregoing, the study therefore argues that since the social insecurity in the region has negatively impacted on the development of the Niger Delta Region, especially on the tourism and hospitality industries from 2004 to 2009, it is therefore the objective of this study to analyze the impact of social insecurity on the development of tourism and hospitality industry in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria. To this effect, this study has the following the specific objectives:

- (i) To ascertain the prevalence of social insecurity on the development of tourism and hospitality industries
- (ii) To examine the impact of social insecurity on the level of foreign direct investment in the tourism and hospitality industries
- (iii) To determine the impact of social insecurity on employment creation in the tourism and hospitality industries

1.3 Hypotheses

In the attempt to achieve these objectives, three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. These are:

- (i) There is a difference between the prevalence of social insecurity and the patronage of tourism and hospitality industries
- ii). There is a difference between the impact of social insecurity and the level of foreign direct investment in the tourism and hospitality industries
- iii). There is a difference between the impact of social insecurity and employment generations in the tourism and hospitality industries

Since the general target of this study is to examine the impact of social insecurity on the development of tourism in the Niger delta with the view to improving the socio-economic development, foreign investment, creation of employment opportunities. Based on this, the study offers the following significant contributions to tourism development:

- a) It will stem the impact of social insecurity and ensure that the Niger Delta region in particular is in dire need of development and if development is hinged on foreign direct investment, then social order will be required to attract it.
- b) Secondly, it will improve the level of social security and create employment opportunities thereby reducing the high level of unemployment which will, in turn, decrease youth restiveness and social disorder.
- c) Finally, it will encourage local or indigenous industries, particularly in the tourism and hospitality industries to be established and sustained under an ordered and socially stable atmosphere. In this case, there will be improvement in socio-economic development of the Niger Delta

In general, the study will serve as a stepping stone for initiating other researchers in a wider scale on the same issue or related as a means to improve the impact of social insecurity on the development of tourism in the Niger Delta.

II. Theoretical framework

2.1 Political Economy Approach

The political economy approach is an approach which is increasingly gaining prominence in sociological and academic analyses [23]. It is an approach which is increasingly gaining prominence in sociological and academic analyses. Its ability to handle contemporary and nutty issues is interestingly overbearing. What is even more, the issue being discussed can be properly located within the political economy perspective. The issue of social instability in the Niger delta could easily be located within the class structure of the Nigerian social formation, albeit, the Niger Delta region. This entails that some people benefit from the ongoing political arrangements while others do not. Those who benefit want to benefit through any available means, hence the class struggle and the ensuring social instability. According to Ake [3], those who are economically privileged tend to be interested in preserving the existing social order; and those who are disadvantaged by the social order, particularly its distribution of wealth, have a strong interest in changing the social order.

The political economy approach raises some fundamental issues which affect the individual in one way or the other. It is in this line of thought that Ekpenyong [15] argues that the political economy approach seeks to know who benefits from the various decisions and how structures and policies of government affect different sectors of the population. In understanding the social instability in the Niger Delta which impacts one way or the other on the industrial development of the region, the *cui bono* question has to be raised and placed against the backdrop of the on-going system of production and capitalist social relations. According to Engels cited in Ugwulebo [38], "the materialist conception of history starts from the principle that production and exchange of things produced is the basis of every social order; that in every society which has appeared in history, the distribution of wealth and with it the division of society into classes or estates are dependent upon what is produced, how it is produced, and how the products are exchanged. Accordingly, the ultimate causes of all social changes and political revolution are to be sought, not in men's brains, not in their growing insight with external truth and justice but in the changes in the mode of production and exchange. They are to be sought, not in philosophy, but in the economics of each particular epoch."

This is because man is first an economic being. He has to meet his economic needs before he can be anything in life. The primacy of economic factors in determining man's behaviour has been adumbrated upon by scholars. Ake [3] for instance, contends that economic need is man's most fundamental need. Unless man is able to meet this need, he cannot exist in the first place. Man must eat before he can do anything else – before he can worship, pursue culture or become an economist. In the Niger Delta region, several people cannot meet their economic needs. In the face of this, some people live in conspicuous consumption. Invariably, the opulence of some people share border with the squalor of others. What is even more agonizing is the fact that their area has been subjected to decades of environmental degradation and suffering without the government doing anything to improve their socio-economic conditions hence the social insecurity in the region. Evidently, since the development cannot strive in a state of social insecurity, the tourism sector of the economy was the first casualty

as tourists ceased to consider the region as a safe place. It is under this perspective that the Political Economy Approach (PEA) that is materialistic oriented becomes relevant in examining man and his existence within the environment he resides -- Niger Delta region.

In the Niger Delta region, several people cannot meet their economic needs. In the face of this, some people live in conspicuous consumption. Invariably, the opulence of some people share border with the squalor of others. The pauperization of the masses in the face of the affluence being exhibited by the political elites breeds a lot of conflict. In fact, authors are in agreement that the Niger Delta crisis, the bloody and violent character of the struggle by militant youth is directly related to the injustices meted to the oil bearing communities by the state, oil companies and the elites in the exploitation and exploration processes. Their violent reaction was a manifestation of their inner feelings against oppression [17; 27; 29]. As a result, the manifestations of social instability impeded the development of tourism in the area as tourists ceased to see the region as a safe haven.

It is also noteworthy to acknowledge that it is the upper class in the society that owns the hospitality and tourism industry [44] probably because it is capital intensive by nature. Without any doubt, the social crisis in the Niger Delta was, essentially a struggle against the upper class and their investments which they (the lower class) considered as proceeds from their exploitations, and had been a barrier to the overall growth and development of the Niger Delta region for decades. Basically, since the class struggle in the P.E.A. was clearly manifested in the Niger Delta conflicts, the Political Economy Approach (PEA) becomes an appropriate model for this study.

III. Review of Related Literature

3.1 The concepts of social security and social insecurity in the Niger Delta from 2004 to 2009

The concepts of social security and social insecurity, according to Juda and Horst [18] are related terms in which they liken to the relationship between society and its individual members. In this relationship and from the point of view of social security, objectivity is expressed by the society, while the individual represents subjectivity. Social security manifests itself in the resulting tension between the two. The same also applies to social insecurity, although we cannot presume that social security and social insecurity are necessarily contiguous and form a common dimension.

In general, the concepts of security and insecurity refer either to the external state of things, the individual experience, or the relationship between the two. Security is seen as something intrinsically human, in terms of a need, a value and a human right. It is a multidimensional concept dealing with different economic, social and political systems, ideologies and theories [22]. In discussing social security and social insecurity, it is also important to clarify the meaning of the term 'social'. The term 'social' refers to society or community life, or to the idea of solidarity. Thus, one may ask what makes security and insecurity 'social'. One general answer might be that social security is generated by society or community in the sense of solidarity, and that social insecurity is the result of insufficient care, which expresses itself in anxiety and uncertainty. For example, 'age' is not a risk if elderly people are well cared for in the society, but advanced years can bring a sense of social insecurity if those in question cannot expect to be guaranteed support in their declining years by society.

There is good reason for defining social insecurity together with the concept of social problems; hence all the insecurity people experience in their life cannot be placed under the heading of social insecurity, only that which results from social problems. For example, there are many regions troubled by war and terror where life is extremely insecure, yet this insecurity is not directly connected with social problems and thus will not be defined as insecurity with the attribute 'social'. Social insecurity is met with through unemployment, poverty, criminality, lack of social care, and other social problems. The concept of security is a complex and multifaceted one. On the basis of systematic analysis, its content has been clarified in the form of four main dimensions and several levels.

Social security is based on various combinations of four elements. On the personal side, social insecurity is a matter of incompetence and lack of trust; from the society side, social incompetence is connected with social risks and inadequate social protection against them. People's expectations of social protection generated by

society do not only apply to their personal needs regarding social risks but also to the needs of others for whom they are responsible, especially their family members. Different social risks threaten people's lives, health and self-fulfilment, i.e. their quality of life in terms of adequate needs satisfaction.

What is social insecurity as an individual's subjective experience? As a psychological statement it will be operationalized in terms of 'fears, psychosomatic symptoms and anxiety' [22] in relation to the societal reality. It is essential to realize that the actual issue is how a certain person thinks and feels about their society, rather than concentrating on the nature of the society. However, the subjective experience refers to risks and instabilities dominating the society and influencing people's everyday life. On the one hand, it concerns the needs of a person; on the other hand, it concerns that person's impression of the value of social security in their society. While the amount of risk varies from society to society, an increase in risks does not automatically increase subjective insecurity. As an objective feature of the society, social security refers primarily to the mechanisms of social support and protection in the society. The question is how sure can people be that they will be taken care of by society in their time of need? This leads us to social policies in defining and measuring social security.

The late modern society is characterized by complexity and risks and uncertainties. One dimension of social insecurity is related to the inability of people to cope with the requirements of the time. In addition to social insurances and protection against harm and risk, another key question of social policies and social work is how to help people to get out of the instability and risks in everyday life produced by society. This draws attention to activities through which people's social capacities can be strengthened. Thus, as well as social political action, social security can also be generated through social pedagogical means.

Social insecurity can be measured by asking for people's subjective experiences and mental images or by using objective indicators. Simple questions can be used in measuring subjective welfare [22]. However, using these questions it is possible to produce only a one-sided picture of the social conditions. There are two different areas of social insecurity in a person's everyday life regarding the concept of life management: different social risks, threats and dangers (external living conditions) and coping with them (internal state of affairs) [19]. Both factors should be taken into consideration in measuring people's subjective experiences of social insecurity.

The other side of social insecurity must be indicated by objective quantities. These include not only the rates of employment, criminality, diseases, and other problems but also variables of social care and protection offered by society. Illness can be a significant cause of social insecurity if a person cannot be sure of receiving adequate treatment, and the promise of proper social support for their family. Thus, social insurance and the system of welfare services play an important role in measuring social insecurity with objective indicators. Unfortunately, government on this constitutional responsibility has failed to provide a secured and safe environment for lives, properties and the conduct of business and economic activities, particularly in the tourism industry. Obviously, the alarming level of insecurity in Nigeria has fuelled the downturn in tourism development.

3.2. The social insecurity and the level of patronage of tourism and hospitality industries in Niger-Delta

In highlighting the significance of tourism, Pearce [30] states that "tourism is essentially about people and places, the places that one group of people leave, visit and pass through, the other groups who make their trip possible and those that they encounter along the way". Concisely, tourism is simply the relationships and phenomena arising out of the journeys and temporary stays of people travelling primarily for leave or recreational purposes. Nowadays, the tourist industry is beginning to take on a different shape and contributing massively

However, many tourism scholars in the tourism industry advocate that being safe on holiday is an expected requirement for any visitor in a tourist destination[40] However, it has been observed that places that develop an unsafe reputation can be substituted by alternative destinations that are perceived as safer for tourists. Beyond the obviously unsafe places in the world, where governments advise against travel, individuals must make up their own minds about where to go on holiday. It has been noticed that one of the distinctive features of the tourism industry is that we cannot 'test-drive' a holiday beforehand. Furthermore, judgments about where to

travel are often made on the basis of imperfect knowledge and generalization, and tourists learn about destinations from brochures, adverts and the media [40]. Many people are of the opinion any tourist destination most offer certain facilities and services such as accommodation food, laundry and also security [13]. In this vein, tourists' patronage of the tourism industry is hinged on the following:

- The need, purchase motives and decision process associated with the consumption of tourism.
- The impact of the different effects of promotional tactics.
- The possible perception of risk for tourism purchases.
- The different market segment based upon purchase behaviour, and
- How managers can improve their chance of marketing success.

But the decision to patronize tourism can be viewed as a system made up of four basic elements (i).Energizers of demand; these are the forces of motivation that lead a tourist to decide to visit an attraction(ii).Effectors of demand; the consumer will have developed ideas of a destination or product by the process of learning, attitudes and associations from promotional messages and information.(iii).Roles and the decision making process; the important role is that of the family member who is normally involved in the different stages of the purchase process and the final resolution of decisions about when, where and how the group will consume the tourism product.(iv).Determinants of demand; tourism is underpinned by the determinants of demand and this is filtered through economic (discretionary income), sociological (reference groups, cultural values) or psychological factors (perception of risk, personality and attitudes). While these basic essentials are easily recognizable in the Niger delta region, the social insecurity therein reduced to nothing all these fundamentals that would have ordinarily motivated tourism consumers to patronize the region.

3.3 Social Insecurity and the level of foreign direct investment in the tourism and hospitality industries

Foreign Direct Investments are widely considered as vehicles through which foreign technology and capital are attracted into the developing countries of the world. This is because the developing countries are known for low savings and investment, which are prompted by low rate of capital formation. The need for attracting foreign investment into the tourism and hospitality industries became pressing, as efforts to mobilize domestic savings through taxation and public borrowing are not sufficient to stimulate the required level of investment in these countries, perhaps as a result of social insecurity. Foreign Direct Investment is usually, undertaken by Foreign Multinational Corporations (MNCs) or Trans-national Corporations (TNCs) as the case may be. In line with this, the regulators of tourism and hospitality industries pointed out that the situation of foreign direct investment before 2004 was better because as at time you could have credit facilities with little security, the state of facilities was excellent and encouraging, better condition of doing businesses for foreigners, the foreigners had the free mind to invest in Nigeria and the level foreign partnership Nigeria was at the increase before 2004. However after 2004, the reverse has been the case.

Supporting the aforesaid, in an oral interview, a respondent from Delta State, disclosed that:

the impact on hospitality is so much that foreign investors in the tourism industry had to look for elsewhere, especially at neighbouring places as tourism does not thrive in an environment characterized by insecurity and violence(2).

Similarly, the World Investment Report (WIR) of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD) [47] said the country lost a whopping N1.33 trillion Foreign Direct Investment (FDI), owing to the insecurity in the Niger Delta region. Substantiating, another respondent, Andrew said the decline in investment has been attributed to the increasing rate of insecurity in the country. Reacting to the contribution of foreign direct investment to any sector, it is pointed out that foreign direct investment contributes to the growth and development of the host country in diverse ways, these include; (a) contributing to the growth of the real output direct investment in the production of tangible goods, (b) generation and expansion of business through

stimulation of employment, raising of wages and replacement of declining market sector, (c) support of overseas affiliates by the parent company through provision of appropriate human and material resources, (d) reduction of the host countries propensity to import and efficient allocation of production resources, among others. However, social insecurity has to a very large extent undermined the achievement of such objectives [11; 31]. In view of the above theses, one can posit that Nigeria in recent times has witnessed an unprecedented level of social insecurity.

3.4 Social insecurity, tourism development and the creation of employment opportunities

Nigeria as a nation is endowed with both natural and material resources that can be harnessed to aid the economic development of the country. From this perspective, the significant growth of the tourism activity, particularly in the area of employment generation clearly marks it as one of the most remarkable economic and social phenomena of the past century. In his submission, Okonkwo [26] asserted that in 2002, the tourism industry generated an estimated 199 million jobs - one in every 13 jobs worldwide. Concurring, Akpan and Obang [2] submit that tourism is the biggest employer of labour in the world. In Nigeria, scholars opine that jobs created by the industry spread across the economy in areas of construction, telecommunications, retail and manufacturing. By implication, the industry is generating employment for millions of people and everyone seems to benefit from it. According to Inskeep [17], tourism has a major direct economic effect on employment generation. The impact of tourism on employment affects almost all parts of the economy. Concurring, Eja, Otu, Yaro, & Inyang[14], assert that the hotel industry is one of the largest industries in the tourism sector which has played a vital role in the hospitality industry. For Ugal[37] hotel industry is an engine of poverty alleviation, it generates a number of additional guest facilities such as restaurant, a swimming pool or childcare and social function services which provide revenue use to service other sectors and also for other auxiliary services. Contributing to the discourse, Richter [31] affirms that hotel is an attractive way to generate scarce foreign exchange; create jobs for semi-skilled and unskilled labour. Extending this submission, scholars state that the tourism industry is highly labour intensive service industry and hence, it is a valuable source of employment. To this extent, it provides employment several times more than normal manufacturing industries. Several types of business firms such as hotels, motels, restaurants, transport agencies, travel agents, tour operators, gift shops, car and rickshaw drivers, guide etc. flourish from tourism. Evidently, as a multiplier effect, it employs large number of people and provides a wide range of other business outfits, which are intended from unskilled to highly specialized one. Such other business outfits include recharge operators, restaurants, laundry services and catteries which have become sources of livelihoods. Besides, there are other supporting industries, small and large, which in turn, cater to the needs of tourism industries directly, or indirectly providing and supplying the requirement of the tourists.

Fundamentally, as an agent of socio-economic change, it creates employment and generates enormous income. In addition, tourism contributes to alleviation of the major challenges confronting the country. Based on this, tourism is generally seen as a very important instrument to the attainment of sustainable development goals (SDGs). Sequel to this, the immense socio-economic impacts and benefits of tourism have in recent time been recognized by several states and the Federal Government of Nigeria. Contingent upon this, part of the effort towards diversifying the economy of the nation has been to harness and develop tourism – the untapped non-oil sector [2].

From the foregoing, it is obvious that tourism ranks as one of the programme initiatives that contribute to national development. Tourism could contribute meaningfully to the economic development of Nigeria if properly harnessed [12] cited in [24]. In Nigeria the contribution to government revenue from levies on Hospitality sector (registration and other charges) recorded N1.149m in 2004 while N100m was generated in 2009. Furthermore, N313m was generated by company tax (National Bureau of Statistics, NBS). In 2011, the industry contributed about N1, 232.2 billion (3.3 percent) to the GDP in Nigeria. In its report, the World Travel and Tourism Council (WITC) forecasts that the industry will generate 897,500 jobs representing 1.4 percent of Nigeria's total workforce in 2012 and that over the next 10 years, the amount is expected to grow by 6.5 percent per annum to N483.4 billion in 2022[34]. From the foregoing, the only way to have sustainable tourism is through the development of the entire neglected tourist sites in Nigeria. This would translate to increased

contribution towards Gross Domestic Product, employment generation, improved economic and social progress within Nigeria and Africa as a whole [35]. The immense socio-economic impacts and benefits of tourism have in recent time been recognized by several states and the Federal Government of Nigeria. Contingent upon this, part of the effort towards diversifying the economy of the nation has been to harness and develop tourism– the untapped non- oil sector [2].

Judging from the foregoing statistics, a rise in employment of 897,500, will translate to N252bn in investment equivalent to 1.6 per cent increments and 1.4 percent annually with the aim of hitting 5.4 percent in 2022[48] Around 840,000 Nigerians are currently employed directly within the country's tourism industry, representing 1.4% of the labour force. WTTC expects the figure to rise to 1.6% over the next 10 years. The number of jobs created both directly and indirectly by the industry should reach almost 1.9m this year, according to the WTTC, and is expected to rise to 2.9m by 2022, making up 3.5% of total employment[]. In another expansion WTCC's estimate, Nigeria's visitor numbers should increase by 3.5% per year over the coming decade, with the country expected to welcome a total of 1.8m international travelers this year. The number is forecast to rise to 2.9m over the next 10 years [41]. With about N1,232.2 billion (3.3 percent) contribution to the GDP in 2011; rises by 10.8 percent in 2012 and further increase by 7.0 percent annually to hit N2,690.8 billion in 2022, the Nigerian travel and tourism industry is fast opening up to huge investments. Evidently, the tourism sector has made momentous contributions to the nation's Gross Domestic Product and boosted employment assess in the past couple of years [35].

However, in the Niger Delta region, several people cannot meet their economic needs. In the face of this, some people live in conspicuous consumption. Invariably, the opulence of some people share border with the squalor of others. What is even more agonizing, their area has been subjected to decades of environmental degradation and suffering without the government doing anything to improve on their socio-economic conditions. The pauperization of the masses in the face of the affluence being exhibited by the political elites bred social insecurity. In fact authors are in agreement that the Niger Delta crisis, the bloody and violent character of the struggle by militant youth is directly relative to the injustices meted to the oil bearing communities by the state, oil companies and the Niger Delta elites in the process of exploitation and exploration. Their violent reaction is a manifestation or their inner feelings against oppression [17; 27; 29]

This manifests in social instability which hampers industrial development in the area. This state of affairs led the people into engaging in criminal activities especially kidnapping. This negatively impacts on the tourism sector of the economy as tourists see the region as a no-go area. Development cannot strive in a state of insecurity or devoid of the environment As a result, all the essentials of employment generations including the projected figures were not realizable due to social insecurity in the region. .

IV. Methodology

The study focuses on social insecurity and the development of tourism in Nigeria with specific reference to the Niger Delta experience within the period 2004-2009. It adopted survey research, and gathered data from questionnaires, interviews, observations, and document analysis concerning social insecurity and the development of tourism in Nigeria with specific reference to the Niger Delta experience within the period 2004 - 2009. Four hundred (400) respondents were selected using the simple random sampling technique. Out of this, only 345(86.25%) of them were analyzed. In essence, a total of 345 questionnaires were administered to respondents, and analyzed using the descriptive statistics and presented in percentages. The structured questionnaire consisted of questions, divided into 2 sections. Section A had three questions that focused mainly on the gender, age, and educational qualification of the respondents. The other questions examined respondents understanding of the impact of social insecurity on the development of tourism in Nigeria with a view to understanding the Niger Delta experience. Also, data gathered from the field were analyzed using bar-charts to succinctly understand the threats of insecurity on the socio-economic development of tourism and hospitality industry within the confine of the three selected states of the Niger Delta, namely Cross River, Delta and Rivers. The results obtained helped to strengthen the overall findings and conclusions of the study. The choice of respondents in this study was hinged on the fact that they are the main subject matter of the study.

V. Method of Data Analysis

The data collected were analyzed using percentage, mean and standard deviation scores. The hypotheses analyzed using the Z-test statistics. A structured questionnaire tagged: Social insecurity and tourism development questionnaire was used to gather data. This instrument had a reliability co-efficient (SITNDQ) of $r=0.8$ and it was the main instrument used for data collection. Two structured interview schedules were adopted to elicit qualitative information from respondents. For the test of hypotheses, Z-test statistics was adopted Z_{cal} / Z_{crt} ; with this, the null hypothesis was rejected and the alternative hypothesis accepted, meaning that it was not statistically significant. If $Z_{cal} < Z_{crt}$; the null hypothesis was accepted, meaning that it was statistically significant. Where Z_{cal} represents calculated value of Z test and Z_{crt} is the critical value, using contained in statistical table.

VI. Results and Discussions of findings

This section deals with the analysis of the three hypotheses formulated and tested using test inferential statistics at 95% level of significance. The analyses of the results are presented hereunder.

6.1 Analysis of hypotheses

6.1.1 Test of hypotheses

The hypotheses postulated in statement form are translated into null form so as to subject the hypotheses into statistical test using z-test. In this study, there are two major variables, the independent and dependent. The independent variable is social insecurity, while the development of tourism and hospitality industries, foreign direct investment inflow, and employment generation are the dependent variables. Each of the dependent variables is tested against the independent variable (social insecurity) in line with the objective of the study.

6.1.2 Hypothesis 1

H_1 : There is a difference between the level of social insecurity and the patronage of tourism and hospitality industries in Niger-Delta Region within the period, 2004-2009

H_0 : There is no difference between the level of social insecurity and the patronage of tourism and hospitality industries in Niger-Delta Region within the period, 2004-2009

TABLE 1: Z-test of the difference between the level of social insecurity on the patronage of tourism and hospitality industries in Niger-Delta Region within the period, 2004-2009 (P < 0.05).

S/N	Variable	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	SE	Z_{cal}	Z_{tab}	DF	Alpha level	Decision
1.	Social insecurity	345	2.92	1.02	0.05	3.59	± 1.96	343	0.05	Reject H_0 ($Z_{cal} > Z_{tab}$) statistically significant
2.	Growth in tourism and hospitality industries	345	2.70	1.07	1.06					

Source: Researchers' Survey Data 2019

P = 0.05 level of significance.

SD: Standard deviation score; E: Standard error score; DF: Degree of freedom ($DF = n - K$, where n = sample size, K =number of variable; $DF = n - K = 345 - 2 = 343$), level of significance or alpha level (α) = 0.05 (5%).

Table 1 of the study showed that result of the first hypothesis that sought to ascertain the difference between the level of social insecurity and the growth in tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within 2004 to 2009. The result revealed that z-cal value is 3.59 while z-tab value is 1.96 at 343 degrees of freedom at 0.05 level of significant. This is because the test was conducted using the mean scores of 2.92 and 2.70 and standard deviation of 1.02 and 1.07 for social insecurity and the development of tourism and hospitality industries respectively. From the result, z-cal value is greater than z-tab value ($3.59 > 1.96$). The null hypothesis is therefore rejected since the mean level difference between the two variables is statistically significant. In other words, there is a significant relationship between the mean level difference of social insecurity and level of growth in tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period of under study; the alternate hypothesis that the higher the level of social insecurity, the lower the level of the development of tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period of study is accepted.

6.1.3 Hypothesis 2

H₁: There is a difference between the level of social insecurity and the level of foreign direct investment in the tourism and hospitality industries from 2004 to 2009($P < 0.05$)

H₀: There is no difference between the level of social insecurity and the level of foreign direct investment in the tourism and hospitality industries from 2004 to 2009($P < 0.05$)

TABLE 2: Z-test of the difference between the level of social insecurity and the level of foreign direct investment in the tourism and hospitality industries within the period, 2004 --2009($P < 0.05$)

S/N	Variable	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	SE	Z-cal	Z-tab	DF	Alpha level	Decision
1.	Social insecurity	345	2.92	1.02	0.05	3.33	±1.96	343	0.05	Reject Ho ($z_{-cal} > z_{-tab}$) statistically significant
2.	Foreign direct investment (FDI)	345	2.66	0.98	0.17					

Source: Researchers' Survey Data 2019

Table 2 of the study showed (hypothesis two tested) that there was a difference between social insecurity and foreign direct investment inflow to tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta Region. From the results obtained, the result of the study showed that the values of z-cal and z-tab are 3.33 and 1.96 respectively. The test was conducted with 2.92 and 2.66 mean scores ad standard deviation values of 1.02 and 0.98 for social insecurity and foreign direct investment into tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region. It was indicated in the result that the value of z-cal (3.33) was greater than the value of z-tab (1.96), therefore suggested the rejection of the null hypothesis and acceptance of the alternative hypothesis. It was important to state the z-tab was ascertained at 343 degree of freedom and 0.05 level of significance. In other words, the result of the hypothesis suggested that there was a difference between social insecurity and foreign direct investment inflow to tourism and hospitality industries in the Niger delta region within the period of study, so the alternative hypothesis was accepted while the null was rejected.

6.1.4 Hypothesis 3

H₁: There was a difference between social insecurity and employment generations in the tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period, 2004 - 2009.

H₀: There was no difference between social insecurity and employment generations in the tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period, 2004 - 2009.

TABLE 3: Z-test of the difference between social insecurity and employment generations in the tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period, 2004 - 2009

S/N	Variable	N	Mean (\bar{x})	SD	SE	z_{cal}	z_{tab}	DF	Alpha level	Decision
1.	Social insecurity	345	2.92	1.02	0.06	9.98	± 1.96	343	0.05	Reject H_0 ($z_{cal} > z_{tab}$) statistically significant
2.	Employment generated	345	2.12	1.03	0.06					

Source: Researchers' Survey Data, 2019

Table 3 of the study revealed that in hypothesis 3 tested; there was a difference between social insecurity and employment generation in tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period under review. The test was conducted with mean scores of 2.70 and 2.12, standard deviation of 1.02 and 1.03 for social insecurity and employment generation respectively. The degree of freedom was 343 while the level of significant was 0.05. From the result, the value of z_{cal} is greater than the value of z_{tab} ($9.98 > 1.96$), therefore the null hypothesis was rejected; and the alternative hypothesis was accepted. In essence, there was a significant relationship between social insecurity and employment generation from tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period, 2004 - 2009. This result therefore, supported the postulation that the higher the level of social insecurity, the lower the level of employment generation in tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period of study.

VII. Discussion of findings

Discussion of findings of this study was carried out bearing in mind the hypotheses formulated to guide the study. Each of the objective and its research question posed formed the sub-theme for discussion below. They were as follows:

7.1 There was a difference between the prevalence of social insecurity and the patronage of tourism and hospitality industries in Niger-Delta Region within the period, 2004-2009

The first hypothesis sought to determine the difference between the prevalence of social insecurity on the patronage of tourism and hospitality industries in Niger-Delta Region. The finding of the study from Table 1, showed that social security situation in Niger-Delta was worse within the period of study. The findings of the study also revealed that the average mean and standard deviation scores of respondents on the social insecurity prevalence were $MS=2.93$, $SD=1.01$ respectively, indicating high prevalence of social insecurity in Niger Delta region within same period. Specifically, this was observed in the areas of fear of movement and molestation, and this led to an increase in the presence of police, militancy and other security agencies as people could hardly express themselves for fear of being kidnapped or taken hostage; people disguised themselves, ran away to safer towns and countries, and eventually most businesses were shut down. From the table, the result showed a high prevalence of social insecurity situation in Niger-Delta region and the implication was obvious, local communities were robbed of the benefits from tourism since it led to non-development of infrastructures and also reduced exposure of communities to the outside world.

Furthermore, social insecurity was visible in the high incidence of kidnapping, armed robbery, stealing, cultism, youth unemployment. Earlier Ake [3] had posited that "those who were economically privileged tended to be interested in preserving the existing social order; and those who were disadvantaged by the social order, particularly its distribution of wealth, have a strong interest in changing the social order". Hence the Niger Delta Youth who engaged in the struggles to change the status quo ante did so to change the narrative and engage themselves meaningfully. This result was in concordance with [3] position quoted earlier: "those who are economically privileged tend to be interested in preserving the existing social order; and those who are

disadvantaged by the social order, particularly its distribution of wealth, have a strong interest in changing the social order". In this view, Onyemaizu [28] posited that:

A resort to violence, including armed militancy, assassination, kidnap, et cetera, have somewhat suddenly become attractive to certain individuals in seeking to resolve issues that could have ordinarily been settled through due process. The end-products of such misadventures have often been catastrophic. They include the decimation of innocent lives, disruption of economic activities, destruction of properties among others.(2)

In an oral interview, one of the high chiefs in Boki community by name Eno had this to say: Cries of resource control and revenue sharing regularly rent the air between proponents and opponents. And there was evidence to suggest that oil had given rise to vertical and horizontal conflicts between National, State and society or between dominant and subordinate geo-political zones. Another respondent, Cooker Jean from Port Harcourt in an oral interview posited that the insecurity witnessed in the past years could be linked to relative deprivation rather than absolute poverty. Following the prevalence of social insecurity in the Niger Delta within the period of study (2004-2009), some other respondents (Tourists) interviewed were of the opinion that before they came to the Niger Delta region, social security was cool, adequately fixed, safe, low level of threat, was experienced, the area was calm, people were not prone to molestation and harassment, low level of corruption and relatively good leadership and government policies were formulated to protect the life and property of the citizenry. However, they maintained that shortly after 2004, the state of security in Niger delta degenerated and became grossly inadequate and as a result people were highly molested and harassed; others afraid of being kidnapped, businesses dwindled, and there was fear of movement. Also, people could not express themselves, either. This also affected the number of prospective tourist that would have wanted to come to the area for tourism and hospitality business. Other related businesses also were affected. In the end, tourists were scared away.

7.2 There was impact of social insecurity on the level of foreign direct investment in tourism and hospitality industries within the period, 2004-2009

From the Table 2 analysis on the impact of social insecurity on foreign direct investment in tourism, the result revealed that there is a difference between the impacts of social insecurity on the level of foreign direct investment in tourism. Social insecurity affected shares in business because foreign tourists' arrivals in the region were lowered; establishment of joint ventures with foreign associates including setting up of subsidiary companies by foreigners in Niger Delta region which was equally hindered. The analysis revealed that the impact of social insecurity on the level of foreign direct investment in the tourism and hospitality industries in the Niger Delta region was significant. In other words, foreign direct investment inflow to tourism and hospitality industries in the Niger delta region within the period of study (2004 – 2009) was negative due to the conflicts plaguing the region. Also, social insecurity led to a forfeiture of some foreign direct investment (FDI).

This analysis depicted in Table 2 was in concordance with a World Investment Report (WIR) of the United Nations Conference on Trade and Development (UNCTAD)[41]. According to the body, the domestic economy lost a whopping N1.33trillion estimate of foreign direct investment (FDI) owing to the activities of militants. In response to this, a respondent from Delta State, in an oral interview remarked that:

The impact on hospitality is so much that foreign investors in the tourism industry had to look for elsewhere, especially at neighbouring places as tourism does not thrive in an environment characterized by insecurity and violence(3).

In all, several other studies reveal that foreign direct investments contributed positively to growth and development of Nigeria's economy [4; 6; 25; 7]. Bakare[9] posited that there was "a positive relationship between multinational direct investment and economic growth in Nigeria. By this implication, Bakare [9]

argued that “one per cent (1%) rise in multinational direct investments will cause as much as 80% growth in gross domestic product (GDP)”. Basically, the use of foreign capital is considered as an essential tool for rapid economic development. Foreign capital inflow is generally perceived as one of the ways of bridging the domestic resource gaps. There are two forms of foreign capital, namely: Portfolio Investment and Foreign Direct Investment.

7.3 There was a difference in social insecurity and employment generations in the tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within the period, 2004-2009.

The third hypothesis sought to find out the difference in social insecurity and employment generations in the tourism and hospitality industries in Niger Delta region within 2004 - 2009. The results of the study in the table 3 indicated that unemployment and retrenchment of workers characterized the tourism industry within the period of under study. Similarly, the findings also showed that employment in allied industries were not on the increases but decline. This meant that the industry on exposure to social insecurity frustrated investment projects in tourism industry which on the other hand, negatively halted employment generations. As a result, this was reflected in the downward trends on employment generations, and by extension, low demand for tourism products. While the retrenchment of some employed workers ensued, some resigned or relocated to safe areas. Again, the lack of development projects in the industry had a toll on the non-expansion of allied industries which hindered employment generations for some individuals in the region.

However, in the Niger Delta region, several people could meet their economic needs. In the face of this, some people lived in conspicuous consumption. Invariably, the opulence of some people shared border with the squalor of others. What was even more agonizing, their area had been subjected to decades of environmental degradation and suffering without the government doing anything to improve on their socio-economic conditions.

The pauperization of the masses in the face of the affluence being exhibited by the political elites bred lots of conflicts. In fact, authors were in agreement that the Niger Delta crisis, the bloody and violent character of the struggle by militant youth was directly related to the injustices meted to the oil bearing communities by the state, oil companies and the Niger Delta elites in the process of exploitation and exploration. Their violent reaction was a manifestation of their inner feelings against oppression [17; 27; 29]. These manifested in social instability which held back industrial development in the area. This state of affairs led the people into engaging in criminal activities, especially kidnapping. This negatively impacted on the tourism sector of the economy as tourists saw the region as a no-go area. Development could strive in a state of insecurity and as a result, all the essentials of employment generations including the projected figures were not realizable due to social insecurity in the region.

VIII. Conclusion

The Niger-Delta region had a very intensive social insecurity problem within the period under review. Restriction of movement, interruption of development and normal economic activities were as a result of the fear instilled in both foreign tourists, investors and the inhabitants of the region. In the same vein, the governments diverted resources to fight social insecurity in the region. In all, there was intense social insecurity resulting to the unquantifiable losses human and material resources. Besides, many ambitions were cut short and others frustrated. The results indicated that social insecurity impacted negatively on growth of tourism and hospitality industry in the Niger-Delta region. The implication is that tourism products such as quality of wild life, landscapes and cultural attributes of the area as well as leisure cum recreation facilities were lost. The spill over effect of insecurity showed that many people who could have been employed in tourism and its allied industries remained jobless and this lowered the living standards of the people to decline. In a nutshell, there was a disruption of socio-economic growth in the Niger Delta region which invariably increased the rate of crises, violence, and under achievement of set goals of both organizations and individual platforms within the setting.

IX. Recommendations

Based on the study analysis and the findings, the following are proffered to checkmate future occurrence:

1. The government should direct effort towards modernizing the security agencies and institutions, and also seek assistance from developed countries to enhance the operational capabilities of the Nigeria security agencies that would enable them respond appropriately to quell internal security threats.
2. States government and National Tourism Board should embark on public enlightenment to educate the drivers, Okada (Motorcycle) operators and the general public to serves as quasi tourist guards. This will go a long way to boost the security atmosphere that would attract tourists. Furthermore, the local communities should be re-oriented to maintain standard of politeness, respect, courtesy and general pleasantries and made to realize that social insecurity affects the entire communities as a whole either directly or indirectly, and as such should be discouraged through an improved awareness campaign. Also, government should create avenues for dialogue and negotiations, and the strategy adopted should lay emphasis on improving the socio-economic living conditions of the people. The emphasis here is that the political interest of these people must be taken into consideration while their welfare must not be undermined.
3. The Nigerian government should address the socio-economic deprivation and as well as the inequality which provoked the social insecurity as experienced in the Niger Delta region. Put it clearly, the prevalence of poverty, unequal access to resources, large youth populations with limited access to education or jobs, and other socio-political factors which contributed to conflict and instability in the region should be addressed. Nevertheless, it is the presence of small arms that escalates conflicts from situations of tension to high levels of violence. Since this scenario results in an internal arms race, government should critically address the welfare and development needs of the people of the Niger Delta region to ward-off unrest and resolve conflicts.
4. As a socio-economic activity that has the potential to raise the standards of living and by implication, eradicate abject poverty among rural communities in the region, government should create awareness to ensure that peace, safety and social security are seen as a priori for the attractiveness, growth and competitiveness of tourism destinations in the Niger Delta.

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